

Societal impact report

Deliverable 8.4

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Summary

Deliverable 8.4 of B-WaterSmart – Societal Impact Report provides a detailed summary of the monitoring and documentation of the project’s societal impact, including related information gathered from the different WPs on the contribution of SSH experts (Social Sciences and Humanities) to their respective tasks and achievements.

D8.4 is composed of three main parts:

- 1) Assessment of the integration of SSH in the activities of B-WaterSmart during the project (section 2), across the different work packages and in the Living Labs.
- 2) The methodology established for monitoring the societal impact of the project during its implementation, over the near term (2024) and the longer term (section 3).
- 3) Data on the societal impact of B-WaterSmart (section 4), drawing from the assessment model introduced in M18. This includes qualitative and quantitative data that had been identified as relevant to measure impact during the different stages of the project and beyond its term.

D8.4 closes with a set of recommendations for maximising the societal impact of B-WaterSmart, even beyond its duration and for other projects (section 5). These recommendations are focused on the dissemination of results, the continuity of the CoPs, and citizen engagement.

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Lead beneficiary	Deliverable author(s)
ICS-UL (SSH Manager)	Luísa Schmidt
Quality assurance	
ICS-UL	Ana Delicado
LNEC	Margarida Rebelo
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Date	History of Changes
Oct 2024	Revised version: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Table of contents was updated; text was revised for a public audience. • The executive summary was restructured to highlight the key learnings. • The conclusions were revised, to better specify how the social impact indicators reviewed in section 2 were relevant for assessing the impacts of the project; a section was added (5.1) with key recommendations.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

CE	Circular Economy
CoP	Community of Practice
EI	Expected Impacts
ENOLL	European Network of Living Labs
EC	European Commission
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LL	Living Lab
PAB	Project Advisory Board
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SO	Strategic Objectives
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
STEM	Science, technology, engineering, and mathematics
WE	Water Europe
WOLL	Water-Oriented Living Lab
WP	Work Package
WWTP	Wastewater treatment plant

1 Executive summary

This Societal Impact Report (D8.4) summarises the monitoring and documentation of the project's contribution towards a water-smart society.

This report is composed of main parts:

- 1) assessment of integration of the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) in the activities of B-WaterSmart during the project (section 2);
- 2) methodology for monitoring the societal impact of the project during its implementation, as well as over the near and the longer term (section 3);
- 3) assessment of the societal impact of B-WaterSmart with quantitative and qualitative data (section 4), including key recommendations for future projects (section 5).

B-WaterSmart assessed its societal impacts based on a four quadrant model, which considers the different activities carried out to reach specific target publics - academics, policy-makers, end-users of the project solutions and the public – over three time horizons (during the project, at the end of the project and long-term, up to 2040).

Besides traditional quantitative indicators such as academic citations, assessing societal impact has required adopting a complementing qualitative approach. This assessed the productive interactions between project partners and stakeholders that resulted in creating pathways to societal impact, such as new partnerships and policy proposals.

The role of the Living Lab is crucial to ensure the societal impact of the project beyond its term in August 2024. In this sense, the Water-Oriented Living Labs (WOLLs) are a promising pathway to ensure continuity and a long-term legacy of projects such as B-WaterSmart.

Key messages and recommendations

We offer some recommendations to develop best practices and ensure a full engagement of the SSH in future projects.

- Foster continuity by **raising ownership of projects' goals within the community**. Co-creation needs to go well beyond workshop discussions and the duration of specific projects. It should be planned with a view towards the long term, supporting new partnerships, local initiatives and funding applications for new projects.
- Not every information need and interaction can be planned in detail from the proposal stage. Interaction between the teams and with stakeholders evolves dynamically over time. For that reason, there should be given **sufficient time to discuss the technical approaches from a societal impact perspective**, allowing for reflections and adjustments as necessary, as well as for integrating the perspectives of stakeholders along the way.

- Interdisciplinarity, especially across the STEM and SSH, is still emerging in water innovation projects. Therefore **adequate resources need to be allocated** to ensure a cross-cutting involvement of the SSH. Social scientists should be involved in all WPs and stages of the solutions development, from design to application and exploitation.
- **Make the most of synergies between societal impact and exploitation plans.** Analysing the socio-economic and policy implications of the solutions developed is crucial for future replication.
- **Ensure that resources are planned to allow involvement of SSH experts** in field research in all the Living Labs/case studies, and that there are, as much as possible, local-based team members with the necessary skills for data collection (quantitative and qualitative).
- **Gender balance:** while traditionally there is a prevalence of male professionals in the water technology sector, the B-WaterSmart project has been an example of female leadership. Strive for diversity and be mindful of gender inclusivity when, for example, choosing speakers for conferences and public engagement events.

The above recommendations should be applicable to most research and innovation projects on water-smartness, circular economy and sustainability, especially those adopting an interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approach. Further recommendations to maximise the societal impact of EC-funded projects are provided in section 5.

2 Integration of SSH disciplines in B-WaterSmart

2.1 Interdisciplinary approach

Throughout B-WaterSmart there has been an effort to follow an interdisciplinary approach, where researchers from the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) work alongside Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) experts. The SSH team itself, led by the Institute of Social Sciences of the University of Lisbon (ICS-UL), has different backgrounds and expertise, including sociologists, social psychologists and environmental social scientists with a long experience of collaboration with the STEM sciences in sustainability projects and research.

The WP tasks and their respective milestone reports and deliverables were organised according to the background and expertise of each partner representative. The outline and the contents of the reports were discussed in a series of stages, giving the partners the opportunity to share their own contributions, as well as discuss and refine the results together. There has been a permanent interaction with the B-WaterSmart six Living Labs (LL) to collect information on the socio-economic contexts of each region involved in the project (using a diversity of qualitative and quantitative methodologies from the SSH).

2.2 Work Packages: activities and outputs

2.2.1 WP1: Communities of Practice and LL strategic agendas

In the B-WaterSmart project, each LL (Alicante, Bodø, East Frisia, Flanders, Lisbon, Venice) developed a **Strategic Agenda**. The purpose of the Strategic Agenda was to contribute to the realisation of a water-smart future vision developed by the city or region itself by bringing together all relevant information into one document.

The first step was to define a future vision of a water-smart society and economy and to describe the current situation in the LL. On the way from the present to the future vision, milestones were defined in the process to serve as intermediate goals for reviewing the implementation of the Strategic Agenda. The development of the region's Strategic Agenda was largely carried out through the Communities of Practice (CoPs), and the process of validation followed successive stages according to the CoP roadmaps for each LL, culminating on the presentation and validation of the final strategic agenda.

The approach followed for the co-creation of the strategic agendas is described in detail in D1.4 - Final strategic agenda and implementation plan for each LL after B-WaterSmart (M48), as well as the steps taken by each LL to ensure its continuity beyond the duration of the project.

Another dimension of the project that contributes to its societal impact over the longer term is its portfolio of **training actions**. Training is an essential element in the B-WaterSmart systemic innovation chain, designed to correspond to the stakeholders' needs and expectations (Rebelo et al., 2021). The collaborative design of the training content, planned in close cooperation with the dissemination and exploitation activities in the project, ensures that all stakeholders are involved in the process. The training materials were made publicly available on the project website whenever possible.

Three types of training actions were organised, including: short courses on the project products and solutions (L1); training events complement L1 short courses, typically state-of-the-art or

brainstorming sessions on topics relevant to core objectives and developments of B-WaterSmart (L2); training as thematic webinars on related topics to B-WaterSmart (L3).

2.2.2 WP5: Society, Governance, Policy

In the B-WaterSmart project, **Work Package 5 – Society, Governance and Policy** serves as the central hub for the team of social scientists. This work package, consisting of four tasks, played a central role, in collaboration with other WPs, particularly WP1, WP4 and WP6.

Task 5.1. provided methodology and guidelines on societal and behavioural issues in support of the Communities of Practice (CoP). This resulted in the production of an internal report at an early stage of the project – “**MS3 - Guidelines to Operate LLs and CoPs**”, which was submitted in Month 6 (February 2021). This milestone report was the first output from WP5 and aimed at providing guidelines to support the operation of the Communities of Practice in the B-WaterSmart project (which were coordinated within WP1 – Co-Create and Demonstrate Systemic Innovation in Six Living Labs). MS3 guidelines aimed to ensure that the stakeholder mapping process was socially inclusive and adequately considered all the possible social groups and actors that might be interested in, and directly or indirectly affected by the water-smart solutions developed in the project. Furthermore, Milestone 3 included the ethics procedures to be developed for engaging stakeholders in the CoPs.

The **guidelines for stakeholder mapping and engagement were updated and refined by D5.1 – Manual on Stakeholder Mapping and Engagement**, a public deliverable submitted in June 2021 (M10). Besides including a review of methods for stakeholder identification and analysis, as well as participatory methodologies, D5.1 included a review of the key SSH literature, having played a key role in providing a conceptual framework for the process of stakeholder engagement in B-WaterSmart. In addition, this deliverable was important to update the situation regarding the COVID-19 pandemic and offered recommendations for the first round of CoP meetings. First CoP meetings in most LLs had to be held online, as in-person events were highly restricted for the first 18 months of B-WaterSmart in all six regions involved.

Task 5.2 - Analysis of drivers and barriers for implementation and acceptance of solutions comprises the assessment of water policy and governance, namely drivers and barriers related to the regulatory, legal and governance framework in each LL. The main output from this task in the second review period was **Deliverable 5.5 of B-WaterSmart – “Drivers and barriers: proposal for new governance models”**. It offered an overview of key challenges for water governance across the six LLs of B-WaterSmart: Alicante (Spain), Bodø (Norway), East Frisia (Germany), Flanders (Belgium), Lisbon (Portugal) and Venice (Italy), according to the 12 OECD Principles for Water Governance (2015).

Task 5.3: Assessment of the stakeholders’ attitudes towards water-smart solutions started in M10 and involved the assessment of stakeholders’ perceptions of water-related pressures and challenges, as well as their practices and attitudes towards water-smart solutions, at the beginning and towards the end of the project, through the collaborative work of the CoPs (WP1). This assessment is determinant for the implementation of the technologies and strategies proposed by B-WaterSmart.

T5.3 also involved a direct accompaniment of the CoPs operation, in order to assess the attitudes of stakeholders towards the LL solutions. Depending on the circumstances of each LL, this follow-up process involved analysing issues of social acceptance through diverse methods, including focus groups and information directly collected from the CoP meetings.

Task T5.3 also fed into **D5.4 and D5.7 - Reports on social acceptance and behaviours towards water-smart solutions**. These reports aimed at offering an assessment of the issues that might constitute barriers, or drivers, for the acceptance of the B-WaterSmart solutions across the socio-political, market and community target public. The information herein collected drawn from the meetings of the CoPs and was complemented with stakeholder interviews and surveys.

As part of the tasks in WP5, the ICS-UL team organised a pilot workshop with a group of stakeholders from the Lisbon Metropolitan Area, in partnership with the LL owner Municipality of Lisbon and LL mentor LNEC (National Laboratory for Civil Engineering of Portugal). This was meant as a pilot event to test the **participatory methodologies** and the **online tools** selected for the CoP Lisbon and involved a specific group of follower stakeholders: representatives from the different municipalities and water utilities of the Lisbon Metropolitan Area. As potential replicators of the B-WaterSmart solutions, these stakeholders brought their concerns and experiences to the debate. This allowed for a characterisation of the key challenges in building a water-smart society across this diverse territory, combining the perspectives of urban, peri-urban and rural settings, different sectors and water sources. The goal was to give insights that were useful not only to the development of the Lisbon CoP but can also offer valuable perspectives on the key challenges ahead for the LLs.

T5.4: Guidelines and recommendations for policy & regulation for water-smart systems (led by partner LNEC) started in M18 with the objective of developing guidelines for future policy, governance and regulation of water-smart systems. Targeted policy recommendations for an enabling environment for the wide application of water-smart solutions were formulated under T5.4. The specific contributions to be delivered by the partners were also discussed and refined in bilateral meetings, taking into consideration the outputs of the above-mentioned deliverables and the objectives of D5.6 and D5.8.

A set of four policy briefs (D5.8, submitted M48) provides targeted recommendations for improved policy frameworks at local/regional, national and EU levels. An assessment of ongoing water and CE-related EU policy processes will also identify windows of opportunity (timing and topics on the policy agenda), as well as special concerns and issues to be addressed (particularly the Covid-19 pandemic and gender balance in water-related activities and industry) for targeted dissemination of recommendations. In order to support the preparation of the policy briefs, as well as define the key topics and contributions from each partner, the T5.4 team (LNEC, ICS-UL, Adelphi), in partnership with Bodø municipality, organised a dedicated workshop on Policy & Regulation at the PSB meeting in Alicante, which took place on 19 September 2023.

The **Project Advisory Board member for WP5, Maria Salvetti**, an expert on water governance with the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the Florence School of Regulation, offered insightful and effective support, especially regarding the inclusion of vulnerable social groups such as immigrants, women and low-income

populations. The WP5 team organised meetings with the WP advisor and has received support in defining the socio-economic metrics for the assessment framework (input for WP6), especially regarding issues of equity and affordability of water services, as well as in the analysis of water governance models.

Four outputs from WP5 were reviewed by the **B-WaterSmart Ethics Advisor**, Maria do Céu Patrão Neves from the University of Azores, MS3, D5.1, D5.4 and D5.7, a guidance that was determinant for improving the guidelines regarding the ethical procedures to follow in the constitution and implementation of the CoP. She also reviewed WP1 deliverable D1.1. (CoP architecture and stakeholder mapping). The involvement of the Ethics Advisor in several outputs of the project, as well as procedures such as informed consent forms for CoP meetings, focus groups and local surveys, ensured that the B-WaterSmart project followed a socially inclusive approach in the stakeholder engagement process, while taking into account the most vulnerable social groups, considering gender issues and adopting a fully participatory and transparent approach of co-creation towards the project's vision for a water-smart society.

2.2.3 Interactions with WP4

From the very start of the project there was an articulation between WP5 and WP4 as well. In addition to collaborating in collecting data from the LLs, the ICS-UL leader of WP5 acted as a reviewer for D4.1 - Manual of data specifications required from mapping of actors at the Living Labs (submitted in Month 6). This also ensured the alignment of the stakeholder mapping procedure that fed into D1.1. and the setting up of the CoPs.

T4.2 – Assessing CE options in Living Labs also benefitted from the inputs of social scientists from WP5. The water-energy-resources assessment was complemented with the analysis of the economic, environmental, social and governance dimensions of CE (WP5), namely the insights on drivers and barriers from T5.2 (D5.3 and D5.5) and stakeholders' attitudes towards water-smart solutions (T5.3, MS18 and D5.4). In M36 (August 2023), the team of social scientists from ICS-UL also provided inputs for the definition and measurement of socio-circular indicators for WP4, building upon the work developed for D5.4. and D5.5.

2.2.4 WP6: water-smartness vision and assessment

The WP5 team worked to provide socio-economic metrics for the Water-smartness Assessment Framework being developed within WP6. This work resulted in the submission of **Deliverable 5.2 – Socioeconomic metrics for the water-smartness assessment framework**, which included a list of metrics and additional typologies, as well as an accompanying report describing the process and rationale for the metric selection.

Furthermore, SSH have been fundamental in WP6 in various domains:

- Development of the Water Smartness Assessment Framework, especially to fully understand what water-smartness is, according to its multi-sectoral, multi-actor and multi-objective dimensions. Since there has been little research on water-smart society as such, a thorough literature review was carried out by the WP6 team, along with a co-learning and development process with the B-WaterSmart LL owners and mentors, to discuss understanding of the concept and identify the overarching

strategic objectives the assessment framework should address. The result was expressed in the form of a definition of a water-smart society, fully embedded in contributions from the SSH experts, and after detailed analysis and feedback from the six LL representatives (process explained in D6.1):

Societies are water-smart when they generate societal well-being via sustainable management of water resources. In water-smart societies, well-informed citizens and actors across sectors engage in continuous co-learning and innovation to develop an efficient, effective, equitable and safe circular use of water and the related resources. This is achieved by adopting a long-term perspective to ensure water for all relevant uses, to safeguard ecosystems and their services to society, to boost value creation around water, while anticipating change towards resilient infrastructure.

- The ‘water-smartness’ definition was operationalised into the B-WaterSmart Assessment Framework. Although all five strategic objectives of the project have interconnections with the social dimensions, they are especially reflected in Strategic Objective E – Engaging citizens and actors across sectors in continuous co-learning and innovation.
- Still, in the context of the Water-Smartness Assessment Framework, the contribution of SSH experts also benefited the organisation of workshops to co-define metrics and obtain feedback from the LL owners.
- When clarifying the meaning of sustainability, both for practitioners and academics, the social and governance dimensions were particularly discussed within SSH boundaries. These dimensions include several objectives like intergenerational equity (social, geographical, and governance equity), diversity, autonomy in communities, citizen well-being, and fulfilment of fundamental human needs. Such objectives were then translated into different criteria and indicators that enable the assessment of sustainability.
- Another clearly relevant contribution of SSH was the consideration of the urban water system as a socio-ecological system. This concept is used to describe, analyse and model human-nature relationships, in terms of resource systems and units, governance systems and actors, and how their focal interactions, such as chosen water management solutions, influence the overall resilience or robustness of the urban water system. Such a perspective enables a more holistic evaluation of the social dimension in its interconnection with the environmental and economic impacts of new interventions and water-smart solutions.

SSH experts have been directly involved in all deliverables of WP6 until its term (Month 30), including D6.2 - The water-smartness assessment framework (V1, M24) and D6.3 - Final version of the water-smartness assessment framework (M30), having supported the selection of the final metrics to be included in the framework.

A team of environmental social scientists from ICS-UL and KWR provided the guidelines for feeding the metrics based on qualitative interviews (strategic objectives C and E), which drew from the Governance Capacity Framework. These interviews were tested among representatives from the LLs, with the objective of receiving feedback and refining the

preliminary list of metrics of the WSAF. Following the completion and analysis of the interviews, they organised a workshop with the WP6 interviewers on 1 February 2023, in order to receive feedback on the process and help refine the guidelines included in D6.3.

2.2.5 WP7: Communication and dissemination

WP7 concentrated the dissemination and communication activities, as well as the **Water Europe Marketplace** (formerly Knowledge Portal) and, therefore, it sets key pathways to societal impact. Communication and dissemination activities are geared towards: first, generating awareness among stakeholders and the public about the project and its objectives, and second, ensuring that the project results become widely known and are utilised by the target audiences. The marketplace provides useful services for stakeholders:

- a Knowledge Base of collected experiences with circular economy (CE) and water-smartness from demonstration sites;
- a Toolbox providing access to smart applications and tools designed for CE and water-smartness improvement and assessment;
- a Marketplace for stakeholders to learn and share their solutions and network with other solution providers to address challenges at national, regional and local levels.

A list of communication and dissemination activities for five main kinds of target audiences of B-WaterSmart (strategic and technical water managers; policymakers and regulators; networks, clusters, multipliers and stakeholder groups; citizens/general public; and the scientific community) was defined in a strategy and plan, which was designed in the first months of the project and updated regularly throughout its duration (D7.5). Monitoring tools are in place: a shared datasheet has been created in which all partners register the activities they carried out, the type of audience, and the number of people that were reached. The datasheet was regularly updated on the NextCloud platform of the project.

A set of indicators was defined to gauge the societal impact of the communication and dissemination activities. These indicators (table 1) were included in the societal impact model for B-WaterSmart (section 3), and relevant data updated to M48 were included in section 4.

Table 1 - Examples of social impact indicators

Target publics	Indicators
Strategic and technical water managers	Adoption of water smart solutions and technologies proposed by B-WaterSmart (available at the Marketplace)
Policy makers and regulators	Changes in legislation and regulation following to B-WaterSmart recommendations (at the European, national and local level) Invitations to discuss B-WaterSmart results in policy <i>fora</i> References to B-WaterSmart in government and administration websites
Networks, clusters, multipliers and stakeholder groups	Number of articles in professional magazines (not authored or commissioned by the project partners) Initiations to participate in professional forums References to B-WaterSmart in professional, business and CSO websites
Citizens/general public	Number of articles published in the media about B-WaterSmart (including radio and TV reports) Shares and mentions on social media (not by project partners)
Scientific community	Number of downloads and citations of B-WaterSmart papers

WP7 was also the main link for further actions of citizen engagement, following the recommendations from the EC Project Officer at the M18 review. Additional actions have been planned by the partners, especially at the LL level, such as visits to pilots and public events associated with Water and Environment official days (see section 4). A team of social scientists from ICS-UL also organised a three-session training action on citizen engagement aimed at LL representatives and open to the participation of all CIRSEAU project members¹.

2.3 Social acceptance in the Living Labs

As part of the strategy for integrating SSH into the tasks of the Project, WP5 conducted dedicated meetings with each one of the LLs – owner and mentor – in order to discuss the key issues regarding social acceptance of B-WaterSmart solutions, as well as concerns of social justice and equity in face of increasing pressures on demand, due to population density, competition between economic sectors and water scarcity. In addition, the WP5 team developed a conceptual framework for assessing acceptance in B-WaterSmart, across the socio-political, market and community scales (figure 1, D5.4).

Figure 1 - Conceptual model for the assessment of social acceptance

(Gomes *et al.*, 2023, adapted from Huijts *et al.*, 2012; Wüstenhagen *et al.*, 2007, Upham *et al.*, 2015)

Social acceptance plays an essential role in the construction of communities that are more resilient to water-related challenges, such as scarcity and recurrent droughts. It is already widely accepted in the literature that acceptance is fundamental for management and governance policies, promoting resilience and water-smartness (Dolnicar *et al.*, 2011).

The LL of the project have quite distinct characteristics in geographical, social, territorial, and political terms, but also in relation to the water-smart solutions proposed. Solutions such as water reuse, the implementation of smart metering and the development of digital tools for

¹ The CIRSEAU cluster consists of five ‘sister’ projects (granted within the H2020 call topic CE-SC5-04-2019 “Building a water-smart economy and society”) demonstrating the feasibility of a water-smart economy and society. <https://b-watersmart.eu/cirseau-cluster>

decision-support are examples of the diversity of solutions under development by the LLs, which require a flexible model to help address social and policy barriers.

WP5 has held meetings to gather information from the LLs on aspects relevant to social acceptance in three distinct moments during the first 18 months of the project. 1) The first round consisted of two workshops organised in cooperation with WP1, WP4 and WP6 at an early stage of the project, in October 2020, where the WP5 team collected information on possible conflicts between stakeholder institutions and actors, policy and regulation gaps, among other aspects. 2) In the second stage, WP5 held a focused meeting with representatives of the LLs on social acceptance issues (July 2021). 3) Later on, between October 2021 and January 2022, a round of one-to-one meetings was held with each LL owner and mentor for a more in-depth discussion and in preparation for a tailored approach to gather social acceptance data from each CoP for T5.3. This tailored approach included guidance on the most appropriate methodologies (e.g., focus groups, dedicated surveys) and timings for collecting the data in each LL, depending on their solutions and socio-economic context.

Preliminary data on social acceptance were included in the Milestone 18 report (M24), followed by an updated and detailed analysis in public reports D5.4 (M36) and D5.7 (M48), which gathered data from the CoP meetings and dedicated interviews to stakeholders. Throughout the project, SSH experts guided data collection on acceptance and attitudes towards water-smart solutions and supported the LLs whenever required. This analysis is expected to contribute to the replication of B-WaterSmart solutions in other European regions and beyond.

3 Assessing societal impact at B-WaterSmart

Over the last couple of decades, there have been increasing efforts to develop more robust measures of impact for SSH, which might increase the pursuit of more data use and data sharing (Sage, 2019), in alignment with current policies of open access for research data and funding transparency. While several studies concluded that social scientists have a strong influence on policymaking, the impact of social sciences is more difficult to demonstrate quantitatively, requiring complementing approaches (Bastow *et al.*, 2014).

There has been increasing attention to the need for demonstrating the societal impact of EU-funded projects, and an expert group designated in 2017 stressed the lack of a solid monitoring system in place for this:

Beneficiaries of EU R&I funding should become principal communicators on impact – they must be sure that what they do is responsive and responsible to society at large. Communicating on science should become part of researchers' career and their reward system. A communication strategy should be part of the proposal requirements and followed through at each milestone. Stories to be told should be accessible to non-scientists. Beneficiaries should be incentivised to report on impacts, for instance by making the reports of the beneficiaries publicly available and showcasing the most impactful. (European Commission, 2017: 22)

The assessment of the societal impact of B-WaterSmart is aligned with the Objectives, Expected Impacts and Key Performance Indicators outlined in the Grant Agreement. In terms of societal impact, objective 5 is central: “to facilitate a water-smart culture by proposing, for each LL, new or improved target-oriented governance, policy & regulation for achieving water-smart solutions, and by developing and applying practical guidance on societal and behavioural issues related to their acceptance and implementation”.

KPI 5 - enabling a shift to a water-smart culture was mostly operated from WP5, in articulation with WP1 especially. It entailed the identification of societal, behavioural, policy and governance-related drivers and barriers for water-smart solutions identified for each LL (D5.3, M20), as well as providing policy recommendations by M36 (D5.5), M42 (D5.6) and M48 (D5.8, four policy briefs), which included proposals for new governance models (co-developed with the CoPs and guided by SSH experts).

More than increasing resilience to water-related risks towards adaptation to climate change, B-WaterSmart contributed actively to enabling transformative processes in society. This required raising social awareness of water scarcity and other risks; promoting an effective participation of stakeholders and citizens, with co-creation of solutions and policies (co-production of knowledge); building trust and a common vision; and improving the acceptability of water-smart solutions, while striving for a fair and inclusive transformation towards sustainability.

Table 2 includes the impacts most relevant to the societal dimension, as well as their key pathways and outcomes.

Table 2 - Expected impacts and outcomes for a water-smart culture

Expected Impact	Pathways	Outcomes/outputs
EI 12: Support transition to a more circular economy at different scales and different social conditions	Each LL aims to establish at least one CE-based business by the end of the project and will explore market replication options (as presented in section 2.2). Additionally, through the application of the water-smartness assessment framework (WP6) by the problem-owners within the innovation alliance (T1.4) and with the engagement of the local CoPs (T1.2), the conscientious consideration of CE approaches (WP4) in an early stage of the problem-owner's management and decision-making processes will be fostered.	Strategic agendas Business models Training activities
EI 14: Enhanced resilience to climate change	Resilience to climate change will be specifically addressed in at least four out of six LLs through: A: dependence on freshwater resources in scarcity situations decreased by 29 million cubic meters per year; B: reuse of stormwater, leading to -40% freshwater demand for green infrastructure in the city by 2040; L: heat mediation & C sequestration by +15% green areas for public access; 'water-smart for climate-ready' building certificates in 9000 housing units by 2040; reduced drought risks by -20% drinking water abstraction; V: two new platforms enable better decision-making for management & reuse of water & sludge, based on long-term climate-relevance of measures (also supporting SDG 13).	Awareness-raising for water scarcity (and energy security) Stakeholder & citizen engagement in field activities (at the neighbourhood level)
EI 15: Support achievement of UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	Supporting and strengthening the participation of local communities in improving water and sanitation management SDG 5); Assessment tool (online, free) will be used for decision-making; Training of the stakeholders and capacity-building of problem-owners	Water-smartness Assessment Framework Training activities
Governance and Policy Impact	a) Deliver a portfolio of validated and demonstrated hardware technologies (WP2), as well as more reliable data and analytical tools (WP3) to increase water-smartness of economies; b) Support to decision-makers at local and regional levels; analysis of water policies and governance (drivers and barriers) in each LL to enable the implementation of the proposed solutions (WP5, T5.2).	Policy recommendations (policy briefs and reports) Contribution for new participatory mechanisms (CoPs) Productive interactions (e.g., new working groups or initiatives)
Transformative processes	Develop and recommend pragmatic strategies for administrative, managerial and institutional change, along principles of fairness, equity, social inclusion and knowledge co-production.	Contribution to new participatory mechanisms (CoPs) Productive interactions

Although the key Expected Impacts of B-WaterSmart were established from the start, the assessment of the project's societal impact was discussed and co-designed with the stakeholders. Therefore, the CoPs, which are designed to continue operating after the project's end, will be a crucial link in ensuring effective outcomes over the near and longer term (horizon 2040 in the B-WaterSmart Grant Agreement).

The uptake of a sustainable approach towards water management, climate adaptation and the circular economy will always take on influences from other research actions and policy initiatives. Over the longer term, the ultimate goal is to evaluate the progress of the LLs, and even beyond, towards water-smart societies, which may even be undertaken in partnership with other projects and initiatives in the future, taking advantage of synergies with other research and innovation initiatives, in line with the 2050 Carbon Neutrality Roadmaps, adaptation strategies at the EU, national, regional and local level, the EU Action Plan for a Circular Economy, as well as the EU Green Deal and Next Generation EU.

In the face of the limitations of traditional indicators to effectively assess the impact of SSH research, recently the concept of **productive interactions** has emerged (Spaapen and Sivertsen, 2020). These pertain to the exchanges between researchers and stakeholders in which knowledge is produced and valued that is both scientifically robust and socially relevant. These exchanges are mediated through various 'tracks', for instance, a research publication, an exhibition, a design, people or financial support. Moving beyond counting the numbers of interactions, other scholars have proposed a series of **pathways to societal impact**, such as collaboration (co-creation), expertise and social innovation (Muhonen et al., 2019).

Conventional **academic outputs** - such as the number of citations of published research and a number of visualisations of news related to a research project – serve as **proxies** for measuring the impact of research and do not demonstrate, per se, a direct impact on society or policy. A **people-centred** approach would imply tracking, for example, new connections established, new careers created, career changes, and the creation of dedicated departments at institutions. **The Four Quadrants Model** (table 3) inquiries about impact within specific and broadly orthogonal domains, thereby supporting researchers whose work has different kinds of impact. The approach of looking at impact through different domains is not new, and there are other examples such as the Social Impact Open Repository (SIOR).

Table 3 - Four quadrants model of impact (Sage, 2019)

Academic	Has the work advanced our knowledge of the world? This domain is currently the best understood, with many indicators and metrics of impact already present.
Practitioner	Has the work led to an improvement in how fellow researchers are able to conduct their work? This might be indicated by creating new research methods, building tools that get adopted, or creating datasets that get reused.
Societal	Has the work led to changes in society? This might be indicated by being able to tie academic advice directly to changes in policy, regulation, or legislation. It could be related to economic output, productivity, or changes to GDP.
Public	Has the work changed public understanding? In contrast to societal change, this would look at changes in the public debate, public engagement and outreach activities, and possibly changes to the spread and nature of information distributed in networks (from news networks to social and private networks).

Taking insights from different models of SSH impact assessment, we can compose an approach that combines complementary targets and perspectives. The methodology for assessing the societal impact of B-WaterSmart, therefore, draws on the **four quadrants model** – academic, practitioner, societal and public (Sage, 2019) and encompasses four different targets and three-time horizons, taking into account the complementary perspectives of the academic output and the people-centered models.

In sum, in devising a long-term strategy for monitoring the societal impact of B-WaterSmart, it is necessary to take the following dimensions into account:

1. **Stages:** during the project; near term (at the end of the Project); long term (after Project towards 2040)
2. **Scale:** Living Labs (cities + regions); national; EU
3. **Actors involved:** CoP members; institutions & NGO members of CoP specialised working groups (e.g., technology providers; environment agencies); policymakers; civil society organisations; replicators of water-smart solutions
4. **Methods for collecting data** (quantitative and qualitative): interviews, surveys, media analysis, documental analysis (policy instruments)

Data collection was organised to maximise synergies with ongoing project tasks, namely the organisation of CoPs with the stakeholders and the Water-smartness Assessment Framework.

The external societal impact of the project can be monitored in multiple ways, in quantitative and qualitative terms, such as:

- a) Number of references on web browsers and non-academic websites (e.g., institutional and government websites, corporations and NGO mentions) (quantitative);
- b) Mentions in external reports and the media (beyond academic context) (quantitative);
- c) Partnerships with governmental and non-governmental organisations; requests for consultancy and specific studies/surveys; direct participation in designing new policy strategies or legislation; invitation to Project members/representatives to join advisory boards in organisations of civil society (qualitative assessment).

Under a **co-production approach**, the stakeholders themselves are involved in defining the priorities of knowledge exchange, which can result in the organisation of special dissemination and training activities (e.g., workshops) for specific groups (UKRI, 2022). The CoPs were par excellence the means of interaction, interlinked with thematical working groups (e.g., water reuse regulation). Political will, strategy and creativity are key ingredients in building a common vision (Nicholson-Cole & O’Riordan, 2009). However, a process of co-learning and trust building has some of its results only visible over the longer term.

Figure 2 introduces the model created for assessing the societal impact of B-WaterSmart, which guided the data collection for section 4.

Figure 2 - Approach for measuring the societal impact of B-WaterSmart

4 Results

4.1 Quantitative assessment: project indicators

Following the assessment model outlined, section 4 provides data for measuring the societal impact of B-WaterSmart, considering the four key target groups: academics, policymakers, end-users of the B-WaterSmart solutions, and the public.

Regarding publications, at M48 there were 8 peer-reviewed Open Access publications, besides the articles under preparation and review. This reflects the long time required for the collective writing-up and review of academic publications, as well as the fact that many of the primary results of the project were only available and robust enough for publication at the final stage of the project. Depending on the discipline, qualified journals may take up to one year to go through the different stages of submission and review. In addition, most of the papers are joint publications with co-authors from several project partners. While joint publications take time, these collaborative efforts are essential for maximising the academic, societal, and policy impact of the project results, as well as their replication in other regions and countries, beyond the B-WaterSmart LLs. Conversely, there have been already 171 non peer-reviewed publications about B-WaterSmart, e.g., articles on professional websites or magazines.²

Regarding the project website, it is notable the interest raised by indicators of water-smartness and circular economy, as well as the process of implementing CoPs and the analysis of water governance models, among the most sought information from B-WaterSmart results. The deliverables on table 4 are among the most downloaded from the website³.

Table 4 – Downloads of B-WaterSmart deliverables

Deliverable	Number of downloads
B-WaterSmart FIWARE based interoperability framework (D3.1)	212
Definition of circular economy indicators for Living Labs (D4.2)	194
What is water smartness and how to assess it (D6.1)	161
Manual of stakeholder mapping and engagement (D5.1)	133
Drivers and Barriers for Water-Smart Solutions across 6 Cases: Policy and Governance (D5.3)	95
Final version of water-smartness assessment framework (D6.3)	87
CoP's architecture and stakeholder mapping for each LL (D1.1)	82
Technological indicators for water-smartness (D2.1)	73
The Water Cycle Modelling and Assessment Solutions Toolkit	60
Socioeconomic metrics for the water-smartness assessment framework (D5.2)	53
Drivers and Barriers: proposal for a new governance model (D5.5)	41
Total downloads	1360

² Updated 9 August 2024

³ As of 20 August 2024

Table 5 compiles quantitative data relevant to each target group based on information regularly updated by WP7 (dissemination and communication activities, 710 documented in total).

Table 5 - Quantitative data relevant for B-WaterSmart impact

Target group	Activity	Indicator	Value (as of 31/08/2024)
Academic	Publications	Number of scientific articles, number of citations	8 gold open access publications available, more planned and available by the end of the year
	Lectures	Number of lectures	29 lectures held
	Conference presentations	Number of presentations at conferences & pitch events	150+ presentations
Policymakers	Policy Briefs	Number of policy briefs	4 policy briefs available
Policymakers & end-users	CoP working groups	Number of specialized groups	38 focus groups across the 6 CoPs; 29 CoP meetings
	CoP + training activities	Results from the post-CoP and training activities evaluation surveys	50 training actions (surpassed GA goal of 34)
	CoP sessions	Number of sessions	29 plenary meetings held
End-users	Marketplace	Number of registered users having actively accessed and used the portal by M36	133 organisations and 301 individuals registered (as of 9/10/24)
Public and citizens	Local events	One local event for the public at each LL; one smaller local event at each LL for the stakeholders.	All 12 events took place
All	Website	Downloads from the project website	2429 downloads of project results and materials (total as of 9 Aug)
	Publications	Non-scientific publications (e.g., articles on professional websites or magazines)	171 publications
	Magazine	Number of issues, number of recipients or downloads	All 4 issues available (212 downloads from project website)
	Newsletter	Number of issues, number of subscriptions	8 issues were published, 214 subscribers
	Productive interactions	LL success stories	6 Success stories published on the website and shared on social media
	Brochures, videos, leaflet	Number of brochures, videos and leaflet	1 leaflet, 40+ project videos, and 3 brochures available
	Social media	Interactions with Twitter and LinkedIn accounts	712 followers on Twitter (X) and 459 connections on LinkedIn. About 300 reposts on LinkedIn and retweets on Twitter (X), 65 comments
	Media	Communication campaigns & press releases	28 press releases available and 6 communication campaigns carried out

4.2 Qualitative assessment: productive interactions

Productive interactions (Spaapen & Sivertsen, 2020) pertain to the exchanges between researchers and stakeholders in which knowledge is produced and valued that is both scientifically robust and socially relevant, developing pathways to societal impact, such as collaboration (co-creation), expertise and social innovation (Muhonen *et al.*, 2019). We have considered these interactions as a key factor for measuring societal impact. These can include partnerships with governmental and non-governmental organisations, requests for consultancy and specific studies/surveys, direct participation in designing new policy strategies or legislation, and invitations to join advisory boards in organisations of the civil society.

Based on our assessment model (figure 2), we also include information on the focus groups organised as part of the CoPs, besides the plenary meetings. Besides being involved in the CoP meetings, **policymakers** and **end-users** have been integrated into specific working groups or focus groups, with the objective of receiving feedback on the solutions under development, as well as identifying drivers and possible barriers for their implementation across specific sectors such as industry, housing and agriculture. Focus groups generally met in between the plenary CoP meetings, to discuss specific topics with a target sub-group.

The CoP Roadmaps identified the main focus groups and indicated their planned meetings. Besides the 29 CoP general meetings held, 38 specialised focus groups have met to address specific matters of regulation, market uptake and acceptability regarding the solutions under development in the LL. Examples of this focused approach are the work that has been developed by Bodø to promote the adoption of blue-green infrastructures into municipal planning (including training courses), as well as the dedicated work developed by LL Alicante and Flanders with farmers at the local level in Mechelen, respectively for supporting the implementation of water reuse and new models of governance for stormwater management. LL Lisbon organised working groups with municipal staff, housing and construction stakeholders (climate-ready certificates) and policymakers (recommendations for policy and regulation). In East Frisia, sub-groups were organised within the CoP meetings, and Venice followed a more intensive calendar of CoP meetings, with four focus groups meeting weekly and in parallel to the general CoPs.

Regarding **public and citizen** engagement and following up on the M18 review recommendations from the EC reviewers, partner ICS-UL proposed and organised a series of training sessions on citizen engagement aimed at LL representatives but also open to other CIRSEAU projects. The objective was to support and inspire the organisation of events for public and citizen engagement by the LLs, as well as other initiatives held by water-smart projects. We involved the CIRSEAU partners to maximise resources and have an opportunity to develop synergies and exchange ideas on innovative approaches and best practices for engaging citizens in the fields of water innovation, circular economy and adaptation to climate change. A wide diversity of organisations attended, including water utilities, municipalities, research organisations and technology providers (water and energy).

Within WP7, at least two local events were planned for each LL, at least one of them organised in collaboration with Water Europe (Table 6).

Table 6 - Public events at the Living Labs

Alicante
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local event with citizen engagement at the World Environment Day, organised with the Consumers' Association of Alicante. Project presentation and visit to the demonstration site. Citizen Engagement Event (May 29th – June 9th) in the Water Museum of Alicante, organised together with Water Europe. The event started with the last B-WaterSmart CoP on the 29th of May, and it went on with an exhibition showing the project's highlights which remained open until the 9th of June. During this period, 1,192 visitors of all ages visited the exhibition. Scheduled guided visits for schools, which included quiz contests on water sustainability and demonstrative experiments were also organised during the first week.
Bodø
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recycle week (Gjenbruksuka) in 15th of September 2023 – water issues at national, but also international level, exhibit smart meters and dashboard in collab with WE and a stand in public on the 16th for general awareness. A second event on World Water Day 2024: A school outing to the local water treatment facility with additional lessons on raising general water awareness.
East Frisia
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open Door Day (June 2022) Local Even Lohne (June 2024): results of the drinking water network flow measurements were shown and explained to the citizens of Lohne.
Flanders
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 23.10.2022 - Pumpkin for Citizens local event took place (City of Mechelen and Proefstation). 22.10.2023 - Pumpkin 2.0 event: opening of the buffer basin (City of Mechelen & Proefstation) 06.06.2024 LL Flanders final event organised with WE, aimed at water professionals, focused on a robust drinking water production and on smart buffering and rainwater reuse for agriculture (WE, VLAKWA, Vito, KWR, Aquafin, De Watergroep, Proefstation, Mechelen). 14.07.2024 'Big Jump' public event for citizen engagement (City of Mechelen)
Lisbon
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two events took place in July 2023, organised by ICS-UL, with high school students: summer traineeships of the national outreach programme Ciência Viva and Summer traineeships of the University of Lisbon. The main topic was water reuse in the city of Lisbon. On World Water Day 2024, the Municipality of Lisbon (CML), LNEC and Water Europe organised an event where solutions developed by the Lisbon LL were showcased and the Lisbon WOLL, integrated in the "Atlas of EU Water-Oriented Living Labs", was presented. LNEC and CML organised an activity with 127 students from 7 classes of three elementary schools. The sessions worked as a role-playing game where the children acted as the LL team. 80 ideas were displayed at the World Water Day event on 22 March 2024.
Venice
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Event on 6-7 December 2023 with WE. The first day was dedicated to the CoP and issues on water-related challenges from the EU perspective. The morning of the second day was dedicated to citizen awareness, with an event organised at the Ca' Foscari University. In the afternoon the focus was on creating synergies with the ULTIMATE sister project for a "Water Europe exploitation event". LL Public event 17-07-2024, joint event with the CoP and the final meeting of B-WaterSmart.

The B-WaterSmart LLs contributed for changes in legislation and regulation, the adoption of technologies and tools, and partnerships that emerged from the CoP stakeholder engagement process. The information below is based on the featured 'success stories' on the B-WaterSmart website (<https://b-watersmart.eu/news>) and other information provided by the LLs.

LL Venice has been supporting the co-development of the DSS platforms for water and sludge reuse in the CoPs and dedicated focus groups that meet regularly, in order to analyse data needs and availabilities, and to help find the right source or alternative solution to fill eventual gaps between availability and needs. The strategic planning and agenda within the project resulted therefore from the comparison and integration of the several intentions/action programmes of utilities managing the water service, authorities and other key organisations of the regional territory; thus, from all the CoP meetings held (including pre-sharing meetings with the institution top roles, which lasted about 6 months in 2021). The development of the case study, particularly regarding the construction of the DSS tools, the objectives, means, obstacles, and solutions was discussed and shared within the CoP. The opinions and positions of the key stakeholders were taken into account when designing each aspect of the solutions.

Having started in the summer of 2021, the agenda of the Venice case study has been cited in the waste management plan of the Veneto Region (published in 2022) and in other official documents for strategic plans (Viveracqua Position Document), as one of the milestones for the choice of the sludge valorisation strategies in the region. The Living Lab Venice objectives on sludge valorisation were considered in the update of the Regional Management Plan for Urban and Special Waste (DGR n. 988 del 09.08.2022).

The momentum for water reuse also certainly surged after the droughts that hit the country in the Summer of 2022. The Venice CoP was critical in issuing recommendations for **legislation and regulation** that reflect the concerns of the stakeholders from different economic sectors, during the consultation on the new national legislation for water reuse (June 2023), which transposed the EU Regulation 741/2020.

In Alicante, the focus was on converting wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) into biofactories, obtaining reclaimed water for reuse, producing renewable energy and recovering nutrients in the form of fertilisers that can be reintroduced into the value chain. The six CoP meetings held in Alicante have gathered local administration representatives with consumers and stakeholders actively interested in the outcome of the technologies tested in the LL: potential end-users for the ammonia recovery processes, such as the fertiliser producer Medifer and the international concrete producer CEMEX; several associations of local farmers which strongly support water reuse; and food industry representatives (Helados Alacant, Mercalicante) which collaborated in the co-digestion pilot. In some cases (e.g., co-digestion), the process of pilot upscaling is already ongoing with the participation of the same stakeholders that took part in the CoPs and the pilots. Administrative and legal barriers, as well as strategies to overcome them, were also discussed at length with representatives of the local and regional administration during the CoP meetings.

The experience and conclusions of the CoPs triggered other key decisions, such as the launch of Alicante's Sandbox for the water cycle with the support of the regional Innovation Agency,

and the start of the process for Alicante to become part of the Water Oriented Living Labs (WOLL) network.

The decision support tool Re-Actor developed by the LL of Alicante will also help to assess the impact, benefits and costs of implementing different CE solutions for the urban water cycle, by allowing the comparison of different future scenarios with the current situation.

LL East Frisia developed a regional supply demand matching tool that will help to match water demand and alternative resources in the region. The Oldenburg-East Frisian Water Board (OOWV) has been measuring the flow in drinking water grit via smart metering technology in three districts in the city of Lohne, as part of a B-WaterSmart pilot installation. The data is used for the short-term demand forecast tool to create consumption forecasts, thus optimising the operation of waterworks.

The LLs and CoPs have made it possible to develop a strategic roadmap towards a water-smart region, a common vision jointly developed by the stakeholders. This process has enabled an exchange between all participants on how the vision can be achieved together and has paved the way for joint implementation. As a result, OOWV was invited to present the solutions developed by LL East Frisia at the "Woche der Umwelt" event in June 2024, hosted by the German Federal President Frank-Walter Steinmeier and the DBU, Deutsche Bundesstiftung Umwelt. This year's event, under the theme "Together for climate neutrality", hosted around 12,000 participants.

Paramount to the societal impact of B-WaterSmart over the long-term is the collaboration with the European Network of Living Labs (ENOLL) and Water Europe. As of August 2024, the municipalities of Lisbon and Mechelen (LL Flanders) had joined as Water-Oriented Living Labs (WOLLs), ensuring the continuity of stakeholder and citizen engagement beyond the term of B-WaterSmart, as well as the replication of the technologies and tools developed during the project. The new WOLLs are featured in the European Atlas of the Water4All partnership (Water4All, 2024).

Lisbon took the visit of the Pope in August 2023 as an opportunity to demonstrate the LL solutions regarding water reuse, as well as an opportunity to raise awareness of water scarcity. During the celebrations of World Youth Day, 1,5 million pilgrims were welcomed in a park irrigated with reclaimed water (38 ha), a new green space that replaced a landfill decommissioned in the 1990s, next to the B-WaterSmart pilot in Parque das Nações (Beirolas WWTP). This area, located near Parque Tejo (an initial Lisbon Living Lab pilot) and Beirolas Water Resource Recovery Facility, was irrigated with reclaimed water to promote faster meadow growth. Therefore, it was used as an additional pilot for demonstrating the use of the B-WaterSmart tools. This type of real-life demonstration is essential to expand water reuse for urban purposes in the future, contributing to a water-smart society and to climate adaptation.

In Lisbon, there was a dedicated effort to extend the CoP to the other municipalities of the Lisbon Metropolitan Area (AML, 17 municipalities besides Lisbon north and south of the Tagus river). The first workshop of the Lisbon CoP (pilot online workshop in July 2021) was targeted at representatives of municipalities and water utilities of the AML. These have been invited to all the CoPs during the project, as followers and potential replicators of the B-WaterSmart solutions. The final CoP event in May 2024 was dedicated to discussing the continuity of the CoP in the scope of the WOLL, engaging the AML municipalities in future plans and activities.

LL Flanders is involved in the demonstration of a new system for stormwater retention that will be operated with the collaboration of local farmers in Mechelen. This demonstration is prompting new governance arrangements that may be replicated in the future in other regions and countries, enabling an impactful contribution to sustainable food production, through engaging the agriculture sector in actively pursuing smart management and use of stormwater run-off. This has been made possible by the City of Mechelen through cooperation between PIDPA in charge of the operational issues and support from Aquafin, Vito and PSKW.

During a meeting with the Flanders Environmental Agency (Vlaamse Milieumaatschappij, VMM) about water reuse (among other things) the BWS Mechelen pilot was presented, and the government officials showed interest in upscaling the project's stormwater reuse concept to other basins in Flanders as well and making them multifunctional for the entire region. Potential governance models and possible financing mechanisms were discussed during a dedicated CoP meeting in November 2023. In parallel with other initiatives (Blue Future Limburg and Deeper Blue), the relevant data was provided for the risk assessment and monitoring, which demonstrates the possibility of providing the required assessments to the Flemish drinking water regulator to comply with new drinking water regulation (January 2022).

For LL Bodø, a key focus was smart water metering, and the municipality maintained director contacts with households in a pilot area, to explain the advantages of real-time measurement of water consumption, as well as conducting a survey on “knowledge, attitudes and practices regarding water management” among citizens of Bodø (results included in D5.7, Gomes *et al.*, 2024). The installed smart meters measure the inflow and outflow of water and sewage in the pilot area, including advanced leakage detection algorithms with real data. Considering that water losses in the supply networks amount to high percentages across Europe (30% in the case of Norway)⁴, new technologies that allow to detect and repair them more efficiently will certainly have a long-term impact in reducing consumption of freshwater and improving water resilience in the future. Two digital tools support the operation of the meters: the Nessie program (developed by ICCS), which empowers homeowners by providing real-time monitoring of their water usage, and the Environmental Dashboard for municipal oversight.

In addition to the smart water meter study, LL Bodø's CoP events focused on local surface water challenges with key stakeholders such as building developers, architects and municipal case managers. Significant awareness was raised throughout the CoP events regarding local challenges around nature-based solutions. New legislation was formed in parallel with the CoP events, utilising the feedback directly from stakeholders. LL Bodø was also presented at the NorskVann's yearly conference in September 2024.

⁴ Norsk Vann 2024. <https://norskvann.no/ledningsnett-og-teknologi/lekkasjer/#:~:text=Norge%20har%20ett%20av%20Europas,grunn%20av%20lekkasjer%20i%20ledning snettet>

5 Key learnings and recommendations

D8.4 described in detail the process of integrating the SSH into the work of B-WaterSmart, across the different WPs. It also reviewed the state of the art, in terms of measuring the societal impact of research, and established a model for assessing the impact of the project through quantitative and qualitative data. Finally, this report provided empirical data to assess societal impact at different stages, highlighting the project's achievements in fostering the adoption of new technologies and tools, as well as improvements in policy, regulation and governance, towards a fair and adaptive water-smart society.

In B-WaterSmart, the Communities of Practice followed a structured approach, with meetings organised around a roadmap with clear goals, which allowed to actively engage stakeholders in co-creating the Strategic Agenda of the Living Labs. This co-creative approach is the keystone to ensure legitimacy and ownership among the stakeholders and future end-users of the water-smart solutions. The dynamic stakeholder mapping allowed to involve new actors in the process and organise 'focus groups' that looked into more technical or specific topics regarding the development, implementation and replication of the solutions. From the SSH perspective, focus groups on social acceptance, governance and communication were crucial to get into more detail about the concerns of stakeholders (including representatives of the civil society, such as residents' associations) and particular sectors such as agriculture. These concerns were reflected in the project work and deliverables, including policy recommendations. They also paved the way to prepare joint proposals for legislation improvement, for instance, as seen in section 4, therefore contributing for the impact of the project at the social and policy levels.

The conditions for steering this discourse into the CoPs have been established, along with the collaborative networks within the CIRSEAU cluster designed to capitalize on the financial and human resources of the five 'sister' projects. Task 5.4 structured these recommendations into training actions and deliverables that facilitated effective communication with policymakers and ensured a substantial policy impact for B-WaterSmart.

The ultimate goal is to clearly exhibit how the insights gained from the project can be applied to realise the vision of a water-smart society in each region and beyond, including at national and EU levels. For instance, this could involve contributing to the development of new funding programs to guarantee the affordability of water-smart solutions for end-users such as municipalities, water utilities, industry, farmers, and households. Collaborative platforms based on the CoPs can ensure the continuation of the LLs in each region and beyond. These participatory approaches can be replicated in other projects and sustainability processes, such as local councils for climate adaptation, to maximize public impact and engagement in building a water-smart and resilient society.

Among the key challenges identified in assessing societal impact is the fact that impacts at social, economic and policy level will extend well beyond the project, and therefore require a continued assessment after its official term. The following section draws on B-WaterSmart key learnings to offer recommendations for other EC-funded projects on water innovation and sustainability.

5.1 Integrating SSH and fostering societal impact

This section provides key recommendations that might be relevant for water-smart and sustainability projects aiming at integrating social sciences into their interdisciplinary work, as well as improving their societal impact over the longer term. It is organised according to the four target publics identified in the B-WaterSmart societal impact approach.

5.1.1 Academic

- Outline a publication strategy from the very beginning of the project (publishable results, potential impact, target publications, writing teams); aim to foster interdisciplinary collaboration involving SSH co-authors; include a post-project stage and plan resources for late publications (e.g., university-publisher agreements) to ensure results dissemination over the longer term.
- Establish a procedure to continue monitoring qualitative and quantitative indicators of academic impact (e.g., article citations, up to 10+ years).
- Make the most of synergies (e.g., with 'sister projects') by submitting joint proposals for panels and communications at key international conferences; aim to sustain a presence at the target regions identified as followers/potential replicators.

5.1.2 End-users & industry

- Replication & market uptake: collect information on meetings held, requests for information and proposals (for service and/or product provision).
- Clarify implications of the water-smart solutions on costs (e.g., price increases of current products) and make sure that future funding sources are discussed with the stakeholders; provide input to future funding programmes (e.g., for installing water efficiency and metering equipment in businesses or households).

5.1.3 Policy and decision-makers

- Strive to have a direct intervention in public policy and regulation, such as issuing statements, engaging in committees with policymakers and submitting written contributions to public consultations (e.g., new legislation and regulation, projects that have direct implications to water-smart approaches, such as a new WWTP).
- Maximise joint efforts through partnerships such as Water4All and the ENOLL to make an impact in current policy challenges in the EU, such as the new Water Resilience Initiative, the Blue Deal and the Circular Economy Act.
- Adoption of B-WaterSmart decision-support tools by public institutions and water utilities beyond its specific LL: register meetings held, requests for information and proposals (for service and/or product provision).

5.1.4 Public and citizen engagement

- Public engagement: for maximising impact in the public understanding of water issues, make the most of official days (e.g., World Water Day, Earth Day) and partnerships with the main public authorities in each city/region.
- Also recommended is the participation in events held by follower municipalities and regions that have been identified as having strong potential for replicating the project solutions in the future.
- Training and education: special attention should be dedicated to students and sustainability professionals through summer schools, training activities, seminars and lectures whenever possible (especially relevant for academic institutions and research partners). Pro-actively support related thesis topics (masters and PhDs).

In additional to this report, other recommendations on stakeholder engagement produced within the CIRSEAU consortium will be useful for future projects (CIRSEAU, 2024).

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Rita Ugarelli (WP6 leader)

Lisa Zimmerman (WP7 leader)

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Appendix: Additional resources

SCORES Project – Social Impact Questionnaire: <http://www.scores-project.eu/social-impact>

SIAMPI (Social Impact Assessment Methods), FP7: <http://www.siampi.eu/>

Table 7 - Resources for assessing the impact of SSH research

Resource	Description
Citations	The long-established primary method of assessing research impact, though restricted to impact on other research outputs
Altmetric.com	Founded in 2011, it now provides a comprehensive API into its data. Tracks “attention measures” for research outputs, a key source for “altimetric” data.
CrossRef	A not-for-profit membership organisation that makes research outputs easy to find, cite, link, and assess.
The Conversation	Mainstream media outlet for topical academic research.
Open Knowledge Maps	Maps links between academic publications within disciplines.
Impact Story	Tracks the online reach of research (e.g., social media, blogs, news) based on the output list of an individual researcher. Researchers create profiles for themselves.
Maps of Science	Mapping domains of research and the relationships between them

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